

VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING WITH BIOBASED RESINS AND NATURAL FIBRE REINFORCEMENT

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1 Introduction and Objectives

Conventional mineral oil-based thermoset materials have been used as a matrix material for natural fibres such as flax and hemp for more than a decade. Since mineral oil should not be regarded as a renewable resource, due to the length of time required for natural creation and shrinking world reserves, attempts have been made to produce bio-based resins such as unsaturated polyester (UP), epoxy, and tannin [1-3]. Combining these bio-based resins with natural fibres result in composite materials, made only from renewable resources, which can be called bio-composites or green composites. However, some of the so-called bio-resins have a bio-content of just 50%.

Natural fibres such as flax, jute, sisal, hemp, and ramie, are currently being used as reinforcements in composite manufacturing. Flax fibres in particular possess a Young's modulus comparable to glass fibres and have also been investigated as reinforcement for bio-based resins. The predominant methods explored in the literature to process these natural fibres with bio-based resins are compression moulding and hot-pressing [4]. Only Dweib et.al. used the Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM) to impregnate flax mats in comparison to other reinforcements with a soybean oil based resin [5].

In this study a selection of bio-based resins were subjected to the VARTM-process to impregnate

a unidirectional flax fibre preform. In general, liquid composite moulding (LCM) processes are well suited to impregnate any type of reinforcement with resin, with VARTM being a commonly applied variant, which requires low investment in moulds and processing equipment. Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding simply means that vacuum pressure is applied to the exit vent of the moulding tool. Thus any form of LCM process in which vacuum is used at the vent would qualify for the VARTM association [6]. However, the acronym VARTM is mostly applied to the process of vacuum infusion. That is where the composite is formed using a single-sided rigid mould to provide part geometry and a thin flexible membrane over the fibre, with external atmospheric pressure compressing the fibre tight against the rigid mould surface. The VARTM-process is well described by Govignon and Bickerton [7].

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

2.1.1 Resins

Four different bio-based resins were investigated in this study, including one epoxy, two UP-resins, and a tannin resin. A hot curing biobased epoxy was purchased from B.A.M Biocomposites And More GmbH in Germany, consisting of epoxidised triglycerides derived from plant oil and plant based

polycarboxylicanhydride. Resin and hardener were mixed to a weight ratio of 114:85, and 1.5 – 5% of catalyst has to be added to the mixture. Two cold curing UP-resins were delivered by Urethane Soy Systems Co. (USSC) in the United States, and Nuplex Industries in New Zealand. The USSC resin is a soy-based two-component system (A and B) to be mixed in a weight ratio of 88:100 and is 100% from renewable resources. The origin of the Nuplex resin has to be kept confidential at this time. It is a three-component 70% biobased system, which is catalysed with methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP, 1 wt-%) and cobalt octate (0.3 wt-%). Colatan CDM GT5, the base for the tannin resin, was supplied by Christian D. Markmann GmbH in Germany. It is a natural polyphenol extracted from Quebracho Colorado (*Schinopsis Lorentzii*), a tree that grows in the Northern area of Argentina Tannin. To prepare the resin, 44 wt-% of GT5 is dissolved in 100 wt-% formaldehyde solution (38%). Tannin is a hot curing system and is mainly used for gluing of chipboards during a press process [1, 2]. A standard chemical based cold curing epoxy-resin (Prime 20 from Gurit) developed for liquid composite moulding, was used as a benchmark. This system was mixed to a weight ratio of 100:26, resin to hardener.

2.1.2 Flax fibre reinforcement

A 305 g/m² unidirectional flax reinforcement has been used due to the good mechanical properties of the flax fibres. The reinforcement was supplied by Libeco-Lagae, Belgium, and was cut into samples measuring 250 x 400 mm. In order to derive a final part thickness of approximately 4 mm, 8 layers were arranged in a unidirectional lay-up. Concerns due to possible thermal degradation of flax due to exposure to high temperatures during processing of hot curing resins can be neglected, because flax is thermally stable up to a temperature of 120 °C. Above 120 °C degradation processes will be initiated.

2.2 Viscometry

Viscosity measurements were made on all resins using a AR-G2 rheometer with a Peltier plate arrangement from TA Instruments. Each resin was subjected to a time sweep at 25°C for 1 hour, and a temperature sweep between 20°C and 120 °C with a heating rate of 5 K/min. The resins were subjected to a frequency of 1 Hz and at strain of 15% without normal load.

2.3 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analyses were performed to determine if the resins studied cured completely after being subjected to the recommended temperature-time cycle. Using a DSC-Q-1000 calorimeter from TA Instruments, the cold curing resins were processed at a 65 °C post-curing temperature, and the hot curing systems at 120 °C. The duration of all tests was three hours.

2.4 VARTM-processing

After drying for 4 h at 120 °C, the flax fibre reinforcements were arranged with a [0°]₈ stacking. The fibre reinforcements have not been subjected to a particular surface treatment, because bonding agents have a different impact on mechanical properties of the composite according to the resin type used. Before infusion, the mixed resin was degassed in a pressure pot under vacuum for 10 min to reduce the air content in the resin. The maximum vacuum level was reached after a slow gradual decrease of pressure to avoid boiling of the resin. After degassing, ambient pressure was applied forcing the resin to move into the still clamped inlet tube. Upon unclamping of the inlet, the resin flowed through the distribution media and impregnated transversely the flax preform. The last five centimetres of the preform were not covered with the distribution media, to prevent resin exiting at the vent before complete saturation of the preform, which may lead to macro void entrapment. Once the flow

front had reached the end of the preform, the post-filling stage was initiated, pressure at the inlet and vent being set to 500 mbar. Laminate thickness and resin pressure gradients gradually dissipate, and the pressure boundary conditions are maintained until the resin was cured.

Subsequently, the cold curing resins were post-cured for seven hours at 65°C. The infusion of the hot curing resins took place in an oven, at room temperature. The hot curing cycle of one hour heating up to 120 °C, a one hour hold at 120 °C, and one hour cool down was started simultaneously with the post-filling stage.

2.5 Mechanical properties measurement

2.5.1 Tensile Tests

Specimens with a length of 250 mm and a width of 25 mm were cut out of the cured panels in 0°- and 90°- direction. The tensile strength, stiffness, and elongation properties were measured according to EN ISO 527, using a tensile testing machine from Instron (model 5500R 1186).

2.5.2 Shear Tests

Shear tests were performed with a custom built lateral working shear testing device situated in a universal testing machine (Zwick 1445). It was constructed according to a device suggested by Lauke for curved specimens [8]. Five specimens of each fibre direction with a size of 10 x 10 mm were sheared in the middle plane, with a cross-head-speed of 5 mm/min. The ultimate shear strength is the fraction of the shear force divided by the sheared area.

2.5.3 Impact bending tests

The determination of Charpy impact strength (impact bending) was carried out according to EN ISO 179. Specimens with a length of 80 mm and a width of 10 mm were tested in an instrumented Hesscon impact tester with an impact energy of 1 J for the Nuplex sample and 4 J for the B.A.M., USSC, and Prime20 resins. The impact was placed perpendicular to the

fibres. The tannin sample could not be tested because the necessary impact energy was below the minimum limit of the impact tester.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Rheological characterization

It can be seen that all resins have an initial mix viscosity in the range up to 1.0 Pa s. Since viscosities above 1.5 Pa s are regarded to not be suitable for liquid composite moulding, it is clear that all of the resins studied are applicable to LCM-processes. In addition, it turned out that only the USSC UP-resin viscosity of 2.59 Pa s exceeds this threshold within the duration of infusion (max. 20 min), which led to a very slow flow front propagation during panel manufacture.

3.2 VARTM-processing

Careful observations were made during resin infusion considering two main factors; does the resin boil during degassing or curing, and will the infusion process compare well to the benchmark synthetic resin? In contrast to the other bio-based resins, the degassing of the Nuplex UP-resin proceeded without boiling. The other three resins boiled even under careful treatment, leading to overflow out of the mixing cup inside the pressure pot. Subsequently, all panel infusions proceeded without problems. Due to the prior boiling, the tannin resin had increased in viscosity and instead of a rapid infusion process due to a very low viscosity, the flow front propagation happened much slower than expected. However, a complete infusion was possible. According to their relatively high viscosities, the infusions with both UP-resins were significantly slower than those with both epoxy resins. As observed from the viscometry studies, the viscosities of the UP-resins increased very soon after mixing due to a rapid start to the curing process. This slowed down the flow front speed even more. The propagation of the USSC UP-resin was almost

brought to a complete stop. Due to their low viscosities, the infusion with the epoxy resins took place within three and four minutes. Since the hot curing B.A.M. epoxy does not cure at ambient temperature, the handling of this resin was very convenient and not time critical. The post-filling and post-curing of the Nuplex UP-resin and the hot curing B.A.M. epoxy resin proceeded without problems. The USSC-UP-resin started boiling during the post-filling phase under a pressure of 500 mbar. Additional analyses showed that this resin also boils at ambient pressure, which leads to the conclusion that the gas bubbles are produced as a side product of the curing process.

The tannin resin infused preform distorted during curing at 120 °C in the oven and cracked the vacuum bag. During curing, a gas, which caused immediate eye burn, was created. After opening of the oven door the room had to be ventilated for one night to exhaust this aggressive gas. Keeping in mind that the production of a green composite should not be harmful to a human operator and the environment, further tannin infusions were not undertaken. Fortunately, it was possible to cut samples for mechanical testing from relatively flat sections of the manufactured panel.

3.3 Mechanical properties measurements

3.3.1 Tensile tests

The measurement of the Young's moduli in the fibre direction (0°) revealed an equal stiffness of the hot curing B.A.M. epoxy and the benchmark epoxy system as shown in Fig. 1a. Furthermore, the Young's modulus of the Nuplex UP-resin appeared to be higher than the value of the USSC UP-resin. As expected from the very flexible appearance of the tannin samples, the stiffness was significantly lower than for the other resins. Very similar trends were derived transverse to the fibre direction (Fig. 1b) with slightly higher values for the conventional Prime 20 resin.

Fig. 1a: Young's modulus in 0°-direction

Fig. 1b: Young's modulus in 90°-direction

The 0°-tensile strength data showed no significant difference between the properties of the UP- and epoxy resins, with the lowest values for the hot curing system (Fig. 2a), which is due to its more brittle behaviour (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2a: Tensile strength in 0°-direction

According to the stiffness measurements, the tannin had very low tensile modulus along with a high elongation. In addition, the failure mode of tannin was quite different to those of the other systems. The epoxy and UP-resins failed due to initial longitudinal cracks in the fibre direction leading to transverse cracks.

Fig. 2b: Ultimate elongation in 0°-direction

The tannin sample delaminated between single plies proving a weak interfacial bonding. This is also confirmed by the transverse tensile tests depicted in Fig. 3a and the transverse elongation results in Fig. 3b. The Prime 20 epoxy possesses superior interfacial properties in comparison to the other resins. As demonstrated by the data on elongation, the B.A.M. epoxy is more brittle than the other epoxy and the UP-resins.

Fig. 3a: Tensile strength in 90°-direction

Fig. 3b: Ultimate elongation in 90°-direction

3.4.2 Shear tests

The shear test results are depicted in Fig. 4. The measured shear strength, as an indicator for the interfacial shear strength, is twice as high for

the Nuplex UP resin as for the other resins. It was not possible to obtain measurements from the Tannin samples.

Fig. 4: Shear test results

3.4.3 Impact bending tests

The impact bending tests show a high impact strength for the Nuplex resin and lower impact resistances for the other three tested resins, as depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Charpy impact strength

3.6 Discussion

The hot curing B.A.M bio-epoxy resin and the cold curing bio-UP resin are processable using the VARTM-process due to their viscosities. The composite materials produced with low void contents (2 – 3.5 %) have good mechanical properties in the range of the chosen benchmark Prime20. The Nuplex resin provides a better shear strength leading to high impact values. The bio-epoxy resin can be regarded as equivalent to the benchmark. The USSC-UP resin developed voids (16.2 %) during curing under 0.5 bar underpressure. This leads to a

softening of the material resulting in a low Young's modulus and shear strength, high elongation and impact strength. Tannin is not suitable for this processing method. The produced sample possessed very low mechanical properties which were also partially due to a high void content (10%).

4. Conclusions and Perspectives

4.1 Conclusions

It can be concluded that two of the investigated biobased resins (B.A.M epoxy resin and Nuplex UP resin) can be potentially be used in the VARTM-process to impregnate natural fibres without further chemically based improvements.

4.2 Perspectives

During this research, the interface was not altered. However, it is well known that the use of compatibilising agents increases the Young's modulus [9, 10]

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